

Research Article

Physico-chemical properties of waters from some Ethiopian hot springs and the risk to the health of the community

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ABSTRACT

Many Ethiopians believe that water from hot springs can relieve from a number of diseases and is considered to be the cleanest of all. The physico-chemical properties of water from seven Ethiopian hyperthermal springs which were at 44.8-93.4°C and with a pH of 6.4-8.4 were analyzed. The pH, turbidity, chlorine, sulphate, nitrate, nitrite and ammonia fell within the range stipulated for drinking water by WHO. Bicarbonate and sodium ions including conductivity values were high. As the practice is not hygienic the water may cause acute infectious diarrhea, repeat or chronic diarrhea episodes, and other non-diarrheal disease, which can arise from the chemical species.

Key words: Ethiopia, hyperthermal springs, Physico-chemical properties, Hot springs, Acute and infectious diarrhea

INTRODUCTION

In the rural and most urban settlements of Ethiopia, spring, surface (streams, ponds, rivers), ground and rain waters are the main sources of drinking water. Many Ethiopians believe that water from a hot spring can cure and suppress ailments (Zinabu G-M, et al., 2004) and consider it as safe and economical. The water is, thus consumed in excess and used as a hot bath.

Van der Merwe (1962) reported that the chemical composition of the underlying rocks, soil formations and the length of time that the water body has been trapped underground determine the quality of natural waters, ground waters and springs in particular. The data from this study will contribute to the knowledge of the physical and chemical properties of water from some Ethiopian hyper-thermal springs and their risk to health of the public.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Water samples were collected on three occasions (morning, noon and Evening) from hot springs at Abaya, Wendo-Genet (Bele), Dilla, Monopol, Shalla/Abidjata, Sodere and Yirgalem using clean polythene bottles (Zinabu G-M, et al., 2004). The physico-chemical variables were studied at the Ethiopian Health and Nutrition Institute (EHNI) using standard methods as appropriate (American Public Health Association (APHA), 1992). Temperature and pH of water was measured directly by using equipments from HANA instruments and mean values were calculated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The location of the thermal springs and the physico-chemical properties of their water are presented in Table 1. The springs ranged from 44.8-93.4°C with a pH of 6.4-8.4. The pH fell within the range (6.5-8.5) stipulated for drinking water (WHO, 1993). All the water samples were colorless and odorless. Water from two of the springs (Abaya and Yirgalem) was found to be tasteless while the rest were salty. Except for the water from Abaya, the conductivity values are high and are not within the limits of the acceptable standards (400 µS/cm). Turbidity in

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of water from some Ethiopian hyperthermal springs

Hot spring/Parameter	Abaya	Wendo-Genet (Bele)	Dilla	Monopol	Shalla/Abidjata	Sodere	Yirgalem
Altitude (masl)	1000-2000	2000-3000	2000-3000	1000-2000	1000-2000	1000-2000	2000-3000
T (°C)	73.6	71.4	60.0	86.6	93.4	59.4	44.8
pH	6.39	6.81	6.40	8.20	8.38	6.25	7.07
Latitude (°N)	6.02	7.19	6.00	7.04	8.00	8.33	6.40
Longitude (°E)	37.36	38.31	38.00	38.31	38.43	39.15	38.23
Color	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Odor	O	O	O	O	O	O	O
Taste	T	S	S	S	S	S	T
Settleable solids	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
Floating solids	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Suspended solids	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
Turbidity (NTU)	0.53	1.39	0.70	0.86	0.99	0.38	0.45
Filterable residue (mg/l)	206.0	1968.0	1866.0	1168.0	5862.0	1922.0	270.0
Electrical conductivity at 25°C (µS/cm)	309.5	2753.8	2742.4	1613.0	9108.4	2699.6	281.94
Carbonate alkalinity as CaCO ₃ (mg/l)	40.0	ND	ND	ND	640.0	ND	ND
Bicarbonate alkalinity as CaCO ₃ (mg/l)	130.0	1240.0	1420.0	710.0	2100.0	1170.0	150.0
Total hardness as CaCO ₃ (mg/l)	144.0	116.0	28.0	44.0	2.0	56.0	24.0
Silica, total (SiO ₂) (mg/l)	198.86	132.95	80.68	175.0	104.55	164.77	112.5
Cations (mg/l)							
NH ₄ ⁺	ND	0.21	0.02	ND	0.95	ND	0.06
Na ⁺	14.45	680.0	748.0	391.0	2380.0	671.5	61.2
K ⁺	1.72	44.55	14.85	29.7	33.0	39.6	5.94
Ca ⁺⁺	38.48	38.48	9.62	12.83	ND	16.0	6.42
Mg ⁺⁺	11.68	4.86	0.98	2.92	0.49	4.86	1.95
Fe, Total	ND	0.40	0.09	0.12	0.04	0.01	ND
Mn ⁺⁺	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Anions (mg/l)							
Cl ⁻	4.12	149.96	70.02	59.7	1602.4	162.0	4.12
NO ₂ ⁻	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.14	0.03	0.01
NO ₃ ⁻	3.08	ND	ND	0.14	ND	0.38	0.81
F ⁻	0.22	7.75	13.25	11.25	68.5	8.75	2.00
HCO ₃ ²⁻	158.6	1512.8	1732.4	866.2	2562.0	1427.4	183.0
CO ₃ ²⁻	24.0	ND	ND	ND	384.0	ND	ND
SO ₄ ²⁻	ND	174.48	115.63	94.65	36.62	138.26	ND
PO ₄ ³⁻ (ortho)	0.16	0.26	0.04	0.05	ND	0.13	0.21

Note: C = colorless, O = odorless, T = tasteless, S = salty, P = present, A = absent, ND = not detected

all the cases fell within the maximum recommended limits for domestic and drinking waters, which is 5 NTU (4).

The springs were characterized by low chlorine concentrations except that of Shalla/Abidjata which is 1602.4 mg/l (almost six times greater than the maximum limits recommended by WHO). High concentration of sodium was found at Dilla, Bele and Shalla/Abidjata. Nitrate, nitrite and ammonia, which are of great interest because of their nutrient values (Dallas HF and Day JA., 1993) were low, while a high concentration of bicarbonate ion was registered in almost all the cases, the highest being at Shalla/Abidjata (2562.0 mg/l). The SO₄²⁻ ion, which can cause diarrhea at elevated concentrations (Kempster et al., 1997) and the rest of the micronutrients were low in concentration in all the springs.

The data from the present study shows that, some of the parameters measured are not within the acceptable range for drinking or domestic water. Consumption of the waters from the spring should either be avoided or need appropriate treatments.

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